

Misleading editorial on the COVID A to Z trial by Michos and Cainzos-Achirica (2021)

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Comment on:

Michos ED, Cainzos-Achirica M.

Supplements for the Treatment of Mild COVID-19-Challenging Health Beliefs With Science From A to Z.

JAMA Netw Open. 2021 Feb 1;4(2):e210431.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33576814>

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Michos and Cainzos-Achirica write [1] in their editorial about the COVID A to Z trial [2] that “*the evidence supporting supplements as a treatment for viral infections is rather limited*” [3]. However, reference 3 is a superficial discussion of numerous supplements so that the text on vitamin C is just 135 words long. Michos and Cainzos-Achirica ignore the Cochrane review on vitamin C and the common cold which is 104 pages long [4], and thereby much more relevant source for information on vitamin C and respiratory virus infections.

The Cochrane review reported that 31 comparisons examined the effect of regular vitamin C on 9745 episodes of common cold duration. In adults the duration of colds was reduced by 7.7% (95% CI 3.7% to 11.8%, P = 0.00018) and in children by 14.2% (95% CI 7.3% to 21.1%, P = 0.000053)” [4: Analysis 2.1]. It does not seem appropriate to describe such particularly small P-values over dozens of placebo-controlled trials as “rather limited” evidence [1].

Michos and Cainzos-Achirica further write about The COVID A to Z Trial that “*after an interim analysis, the safety monitoring board recommended the study be stopped early for futility after enrollment of only 214 participants because of the low probability of detecting significant differences between the study groups in terms of the primary end point*” [1]. This comment is puzzling.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

The COVID A to Z Trial authors described the rationalization behind the sample size calculation as follows: “*We assumed that the usual care group would achieve a 50% reduction in symptom severity in a mean (SD) of 6 (3) days and that at least 1 of the other 3 study groups would achieve a 50% reduction in a mean (SD) of 5 (3) days*” [2]. This indicates that the trial authors assumed that there is 1.0 day difference between the control group and one of the intervention groups.

The trial results were reported as follows: “*Patients who received usual care without supplementation achieved a 50% reduction in symptoms in a mean (SD) of 6.7 (4.4) days compared with a mean (SD) of 5.5 (3.7) days for patients receiving ascorbic acid, a mean (SD) of 5.9 (4.9) days for patients receiving zinc gluconate, and a mean (SD) of 5.5 (3.4) days for patients receiving both ascorbic acid and zinc gluconate supplementation*” [2].

Thus, two trial arms found an effect greater than expected. Compared with the control, in the vitamin C arm, duration was 1.2 days shorter, and in the vitamin C+zinc arm, duration was also 1.2 days shorter.

Given that the observed effect was 20% greater than assumed (1.2 vs 1.0), it is illogical to stop such a trial early for futility. Michos and Cainzos-Achirica do not consider this paradox: how is it possible that 1.0 day reduction in duration is clinically important enough to justify a trial, but an observed 1.2 day reduction is futile and justifies early stopping.

In the COVID A to Z trial, interventions were not blinded and no placebo was used in the control group. Michos and Cainzos-Achirica speculate [1] that “*this could have exaggerated the potential benefit of the interventions.*” However, it is also possible that the lack of placebo may lead to underestimation of the effect. When a patient is given an active intervention, it is possible that he or she tends to observe and report symptoms more sensitively compared with the “usual care” group. We do not know the direction of the bias. It does not seem reasonable to ignore severe methodological flaws on the basis that a reader is satisfied with the results.

Michos and Cainzos-Achirica further comment that “*more adverse effects (nausea, diarrhea, and stomach cramps) were reported in the supplement groups than in the usual care group*” [1]. Here they ignore vitamin C pharmacokinetics. The COVID A to Z trial report described that “*8000 mg of ascorbic acid (to be divided over 2-3 times per day with meals)*” [2].

Absorption of vitamin C is saturated with high doses [5]. Therefore, it seems evident that a large single dose causes more stomach ailments than the same daily dose divided in many frequent doses. For example, 1 gram every 2 hours might have led to less stomach ailments. For example, in the large trial by Anderson (1974), the instruction for increased dosage was “*16 tablets (two every hour) on the first day of any illness*” [6]. The COVID A to Z trial report does not justify the 2 or 3 doses over the day [2].

Some further concerns with the methods of the COVID A to Z Randomized Clinical Trial are described elsewhere [7,8].

References

1. Erin D Michos, Miguel Cainzos-Achirica. Supplements for the Treatment of Mild COVID-19-Challenging Health Beliefs With Science From A to Z. JAMA Netw Open. 2021 Feb 1;4(2):e210431.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33576814>
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2021.0431>
2. Thomas S, et al. Effect of High-Dose Zinc and Ascorbic Acid Supplementation vs Usual Care on Symptom Length and Reduction Among Ambulatory Patients With SARS-CoV-2 Infection: The COVID A to Z Randomized Clinical Trial. JAMA Netw Open. 2021 Feb 1;4(2):e210369.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33576820>
<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2021.0369>
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC7881357>
3. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32334392>
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsx.2020.04.015>
4. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD000980.pub4>
<https://hdl.handle.net/10138/225864>
5. <https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-140-7-200404060-00010>
6. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1947567>
7. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34040614>
8. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35054455>